

PLASMA BALL FORMATION - AN EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE TO TEST RADIATIVE HEAT TRANSFER MODELS IN NON-EQUILIBRIUM PLASMAS

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ABSTRACT

This article shows that a recent discovery in the field of molecular plasma, called Plasma Ball Formation (PBF), could provide a new experimental technique for testing collisional radiative models in non-equilibrium plasmas. Moreover, PBF could open a way to measure the bulk viscosity under controlled conditions, in addition to the sound velocity, thus providing an excellent opportunity to improve models used in numerical simulations of hypersonic flows.

Index Terms— Molecular plasma, hypersonic re-entry, vibrational energy, acoustic plasma excitation, plasma confinement

1. INTRODUCTION

Determination of the heat transfer to the vehicle wall in hypersonic reentry is of the fundamental importance. In such conditions, a hypersonic shock wave (SW) is formed in front of the wall, followed by the shock layer (SL), and finally the boundary layer (BL) close to the wall surface. The plasma produced in the shock wave constitutes of dissociated and highly vibrationally excited molecules and ions. Therefore, heat transfer due to both the recombination as well as the internal heat in form of vibrational energy of molecules is important [1, 2]. Empirical correlations, such as Fay-Riddell [1] or Detra-Kemp-Riddel [3], are widely used to estimate the heat transfer at the outer edge of the BL, at the stagnation point. However, the derivation of these correlations involve certain simplifications, e.g., in the treatment of the diffusion of the vibrational energy of molecules.

Fluids in molecular vibrational non-equilibrium, in particular hypersonic plasmas, are outside the scope of the Fourier Navier-Stokes equations, because these equations are based on the assumption of local thermodynamic equilibrium (LTE) [4]. In addition, the effect of vibrational excitation strongly influences the chemical kinetics, which makes numerical simulation even more difficult [5]. Approaches such as [6] or [7] have been developed to overcome these difficulties

but they only work when the vibrational distributions do not deviate too much from the Boltzmann distribution, i.e. from LTE. The numerical simulation of non-equilibrium fluid flows requires the solution of the Boltzmann equation. This equation can be solved by approximations such as modified Chapman-Enskog methods [8] or state-to-state chemical kinetic approaches, considering a kinetic equation for each vibrational state of polyatomic molecules [5]. However, its implementation for modeling complex 2D and 3D problems is problematic due to very high computational costs. Indeed, the recent PHYS4ENTRY EU project [9] highlights in its conclusion the need to trade-off accuracy and computational cost. Non-equilibrium thermodynamics remains thus of great importance as a means of developing reduced models. The latest theoretical advances such as Rational Extended Thermodynamics [10, 11] or Extended Thermodynamics (ET) [12] are unfortunately not yet completely applicable in practice due to the lack of measurements of the plasma characteristics they require. These theories, which are numerically much less demanding than the kinetic modeling, require, among others, the relaxation time associated with the bulk viscosity as input [13]. However, this viscosity is extremely difficult to measure [14] and is therefore often neglected. Yet, in hypersonic reentry the bulk viscosity can have an influence on the shock wave structure [15, 16]. In addition, experiments are also needed to calculate the heat flow to the thermal protection system – a crucial safety point – as this requires modeling the wall deactivation effect, for which the measurement of the recombination rate coefficient is necessary [17], p. 351.

Experimentally, shock tubes, expansion tunnels, shock tunnels or hypersonic tunnels [18, 17, 19] are used to simulate hypersonic reentry conditions and measure the heat flux. Citing Capitelli et al. in [20] p. 105, "Analysis of the relaxation zone behind a shock wave in shock wave tubes is the principal method for investigation of vibrational relaxation at high temperatures (≥ 1000 K)". These installations are expensive and have their limits, because of disturbing effects such as the effects due to the non-instantaneous opening of the diaphragm or the boundary layer [17], p. 330.

As shown in this paper, our pulsed microwave experimen-

*Funded by ESA Contract 4000136080/21/NL/GLC/ov

Fig. 1. a) Experimental set-up. The spherical quartz bulb containing the plasma in the centre. PC controls the digital signal processing unit (DSP) that provides the pulses for the 2.45 GHz magnetron (MG) that powers the plasma, typical mean microwave power 600 W. Main diagnostics are Hamamatsu C6368-01 photodiode, optical camera Panasonic DMC-FZ8, and CAS 140T Array Spectrometer. b) Optical image of a plasma ball seen through a green filter.

tal setup could pave the way for a complementary and less expensive approach to measure the non-equilibrium properties of hypersonic plasmas. It started as development of a high-efficiency microwave-powered sulfur plasma light source. The active substance is a vapour disulfur. The original design included a rotating bulb, to force convection inside the bulb, and thus mix the hot plasma with the cooler gas, to avoid melting the quartz bulb [Patent n° 5977724]. However, it was soon realized that modulating the microwaves at the ultrasonic frequency, in the range of 20 - 100 kHz, produces acoustic waves inside the bulb that cause the plasma to oscillate so that the rotation of the bulb can be suppressed without the bulb melting [Patent n°EP1876633A1]. An even more significant finding was the formation of a plasma ball in the center of the spherical bulb, a phenomenon we called plasma ball formation (PBF), which occurs when microwaves are pulsed with a short duty cycle, about 10%, and the pulse repetition frequency is tuned, around 30 kHz in our case [21]. This innovation makes the bulb static and therefore much easier to connect to a gas supply system. The replacement of the active substance then becomes simple, allowing the bulb to be filled under controlled pressure with the atmospheric gases of planets, including air, to study re-entry conditions.

Since this discovery, effort has been made to understand the mechanisms that confine the plasma as a stable sphere. In [21] we developed a lumped model with one node (homogeneous plasma-gas mixture inside the bulb) which allowed us to measure the average values in temperature, pressure, heat capacity and sound velocity, see Table 1. We found that two standing acoustic waves of neighboring frequencies are excited in the bulb, resulting in the low frequency beats observed in the light modulation. One is spontaneous (auto-wave) and is spherically symmetric, having a pressure anti-

node (node) at the center of the bulb (at half bulb radius); the other is the forced response and is a non-spherical mode having a pressure node at the center. The spherical mode is directly related to the onset of the spherically symmetric PBF [21].

In [22] we extended our lumped model with a second node to allow rapid variations of the PBF radius and pressure in the acoustic timescale of 30 kHz ($\sim 3 \times 10^{-5}$ s). Taking into account the chemical reaction kinetics of the plasma monosulfur and disulfur mixture we arrived in the result that the rapid plasma radius oscillations are in an opposite phase with respect to the rapid brightness variations. In addition, the model predicts the acoustic pressure amplitude of 180 dB (ref. $20 \mu\text{Pa}$). Both these results are in agreement with the measurements made by the research group in UCLA, U.S.A [23].

The UCLA research team replicated PBF with a plasma device similar to ours. Main difference is that they have a rotating bulb [23]. They have also observed the PBF that has similar characteristics with our device, namely the PBF radius being approximately half of the bulb radius. Their original hypothesis for the PBF confinement was the pycnoclinic acoustic force [24] that is proportional to the product of the background density gradient and the mean square of the fluid particle velocity amplitude due to the sound field, together with the elasto-acoustic force [25, 26] that arises from the adiabatic compressibility of the medium. Nevertheless, this explanation is questionable in our opinion. First, as shown by [21, 22], the mean square of the particle velocity amplitude goes through very small values, at beat nodes. The PBF was filmed at different frames rate, but nothing was noticed on the beat time scale. Second, our calculations of these acoustic volume forces show that they are by far not strong enough to confine the plasma. In this paper, we present an alternative explanation based on the entropy production rate due to molecular vibrational relaxation.

As shown in this paper, our device has the following characteristics in common with the hypersonic plasma:

- Partially dissociated molecular plasma with vibrational far from LTE, PBF - SW (non-LTE conditions, cf. Sect.2);
- Plasma in contact with a non-ionized polyatomic gas, Peripheral gas - SL (cf. Sect.2);
- Vibrationally frozen conditions in the non-ionized gas (cf. [21]);
- Vibrational relaxation on the wall, BL (cf. Sect. 4).

In addition, PBF is ideal for measuring bulk viscosity because the spherical resonance produces high values of particle velocity divergence, in the central region, which greatly enhances the effects of bulk viscosity [27].

The objective here is to carry out a physical modeling of the PBF for the design of a new type of experimental device dedicated to the measurement of the non-equilibrium properties of hypersonic plasma. One of the applications considered is the study of thermal protection systems, in particular for

re-entry vehicles. The development of this new experimental device will not be carried out in the framework of the current project, called Pyc4HypFlight, but will be proposed in a new ESA project.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DEVICE AND RESULTS

2.1. Device description and plasma shape analysis

Most of the measurements analyzed in this paper were obtained with the prototype 1 kW pulsed microwave sulfur lamp described in [21], which was assembled in-house from readily available components, with the only custom-made parts being the spherical quartz bulb, radius $a_B = 15.5$, that contains the plasma (28 mg sulfur), and the in-house-designed and -fabricated high-voltage source [28]. The anti-rejection filter of the standard 2.45 GHz magnetron has been modified for the pulsed mode. In operating conditions, the plasma is mainly disulfur-sulfur (S_2 -S) mélange doped with a small amount of Argon gas. The schematic is shown in Fig.1(a) with the main components explained in the legend. To achieve the PBF phenomenon, microwave pulses typically have a duty cycle of 10% and a repetition rate of about 30 kHz. A more detailed description of the unit and experiments, as well as earlier results, can be found in [21, 22]. The important properties of the bulb-filling medium, that we found with a one-node-lumped model, are given in the table 1. Note that the degree of ionization should be very low, according to [29], but no measurement of this parameter has yet been performed in a pulsed excitation comparable to our case. In this study, we first focus on the analysis of the PBF shape and the vibrational characteristics of the S_2 plasma. These aspects provide the modeling basis to measure plasma properties like sound velocity with dispersion, vibrational relaxation time, and the bulk viscosity.

Table 1. Average values of the properties of the medium filling the bulb, from [21] : the values are global including both the PBF and peripheral gas.

Temperature	1930 °C
Pressure	5.23 bar
Frozen isochoric heat capacity	459.0 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Effective equili. isochoric heat capa.	669.3 J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Frozen phase sound velocity	608 m/s
Equili. phase sound velocity	586 m/s

The shape analysis is based on optical images as shown in Fig.16 (cf. Appendix 7.5). With Matlab image processing tools, the contrast between the PBF and the background was maximized and an ellipse was drawn manually on the plasma edge. The length of the ellipse horizontal (X) vertical (Y) axes were then measured. The parameter $1 - X/Y$, where the ellipticity X/Y , was found to be between about 0.04 and 0.1 (for a

sphere $X/Y = 1$). Therefore, the PBF is well a nearly perfect sphere. In addition, the radius of the PBF has been found to be very close to half the bulb radius $a_B/2 \approx 7.75$ mm. In addition of being a nearly perfect sphere filling half of the bulb radius (1/8 of the volume), another characteristic is a chimney on the upper part of the PBF extending from the plasma onto the bulb wall, well visible in Fig.1(b). Vertically, all the PBF are located almost exactly at the same position, about 2% above the bulb geometric center. The plasma boundary thickness, deduced from the decline of the optical intensity of the equatorial optical profiles passing through the plasma center, was measured manually from the figures. The average value of this parameter was found to be about a quarter of the PBF radius. A numerical algorithm that filters out the shadowing and reflecting effects of the metal cage that envelopes the bulb and allows for the thickness being measured at any polar angle, is currently being developed.

A schematic of the PBF ②, the peripheral gas ③, and the quartz wall (thick grey circle) is shown in Fig.2. An important detail in all the PBFs is the absence of any concave, or cusp, shape on the bottom part of the PBF (cf. Fig.16 in Appendix 7.5), like the dashed line marked by ① in Fig.2. Since the microwaves are predominantly absorbed in the plasma and the bulb wall is cooled by the ambient, the plasma is the hottest and the wall the coldest part of the plasma - peripheral gas - wall system, the peripheral gas having thus the temperature between the two extremes. Therefore, in the periphery, convective cells that, due to buoyancy, ascend on the plasma boundary and descend at the wall should be present. The absence of any cusp structure on the PBF bottom boundary therefore suggests a convective cells inside the PBF that descend in the centre counterbalancing the pressure created by the fluid motion of the peripheral cells at that point. The simplest convective cell structure that conforms the different temperatures in the three body system and the convex PBF bottom shape is shown in Fig.2. In addition, the chimney is the extension of the plasma sheath (boundary layer), which rises to the wall of the bulb.

2.2. Optical emission spectral analysis

Because of the high temperature, more than 2200 K in the average throughout the bulb interior (cf. Table 1), the sulfur is in the vapor form that constitutes of S_2 molecules and dissociated singletons S in the plasma, where the temperature is even higher. A constant cycle of recombination - dissociation processes occur in the plasma, as described in [22]. The dissociation results both from electronic impacts and pure vibrational mechanism the latter being dominant in a PBF as shown by the power interruption tests [21]. The recombination of two S atoms produces excited $B^3\Sigma_u^- S_2$ molecules that relax to the ground state $X^3\Sigma_g$ emitting a photon. The potential energy curves of the two states are shifted with respect to the inter nucleus distance r_0 , as shown in Fig.5 of [30].

Fig. 2. Supposed convective cell structure in the PBF - peripheral zone - wall system.

Fig. 3. Two spectra: a PBF and a non-PBF case.

Therefore for a purely vertical transition, i.e., constant r_0 , the vibrational ground state of $B^3\Sigma_u^-$ molecule, $v' = 0$, relaxes to $v'' = 8$ vibrational level of the ground state molecule. Thus, the S_2 recombination processes produce higher vibrational level ground state molecules, in addition to vibrational pumping [31]. Note that, as explained in [30], the excited state becomes pre-dissociated for levels $v' > 9$. Therefore, the vibrational levels are limited to $v' = 0, \dots, 9$. Also, for the ground state molecule, the potential energy model starts to deviate from the observed spectra for about $v'' > 32$. Hence, we consider only the ground state vibrational levels $v'' = 0, \dots, 32$.

The vibrational mean energy E_V , per molecule, of eight plasmas, four PBF and four non-PBF cases, has been determined. Two methods have been developed, namely Photon-

average method and PEAKS method, both being based on the optical emission spectra (OES). The methods rely on the work [30] where the OES, as well as the potential energy curves, of S_2 molecules is analyzed and characterized in detail. Example OES for a PBF and non-PBF case are shown in Fig.3.

(a) PBF case.

(b) Non-PBF case.

Fig. 4. The emitted photon energies and the emission intensity of a) PBF and b) non-PBF case. Magenta: Normalized intensity $\hat{\Phi} > 0.95$, red $\hat{\Phi} > 0.9$, cyan $\hat{\Phi} > 0.8$, and yellow $\hat{\Phi} > 0.6$. Red triangles: Most probable transitions defined with the two largest FC factors; green upside down triangles: Observed spectral peaks; black crosses: Transitions given by the photon-average method. The numbers designate the v' state (top) and the v'' state (bottom).

In the photon-average method we find the (v', v'') pairs that minimize the residue of equation (9) of [30] with the condition that the transition has a value of the Franck-Condon (FC) factor ≥ 60

$$\langle E_{ph} \rangle = T_e(v') - \left[w_e'' \left(v'' + \frac{1}{2} \right) - w_e x_e'' \left(v'' + \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 + w_e y_e'' \left(v'' + \frac{1}{2} \right)^3 - w_e z_e'' \left(v'' + \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \right]. \quad (1)$$

The mean photon energy is calculated by integrating over the OES as follows

$$\langle E_{ph} \rangle = \frac{\int_{OES} E_{ph} \hat{\Phi}(E_{ph}) dE_{ph}}{\int_{OES} \hat{\Phi}(E_{ph}) dE_{ph}} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\Phi}(E_{ph})$ is the normalized photon intensity as a function of the photon energy E_{ph} . The excited state electronic levels $T_e(v')$ are given in [30] (cf. Table II) as well as the spectral constants of the ground state (cf. Table I) ($w_e'' = 727.848 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $w_e x_e'' = 3.0195 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $w_e y_e'' = 4.196 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $w_e z_e'' = 9.77 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). For the four PBF cases, we obtain that the allowed transitions are from excited molecule vibrational states of $v' = 5$ and 6 to the ground state levels of $v'' = 23$ and 24 . The energies of each v' level are given in Table IX of [30]. In this first approach, we simply define the mean vibrational energy E_V as an arithmetic mean value of these ground state vibrational level energies, since their number is only two or three in each case, and they are adjacent and correspond to close intensities. The values of E_V of the four PBF cases is between 1.96 eV and 1.99 eV, the mean value being $\langle E_V \rangle_{\text{PBF}} = 1.97 \text{ eV}$ and the standard deviation 0.018 eV. For the four non-PBF cases the vibrational energies E_V are between 1.77 eV and 1.85 eV, the mean value being $\langle E_V \rangle_{\text{non-PBF}} = 1.81 \text{ eV}$ and the standard deviation 0.03 eV. Therefore, the PBF-cases have higher mean vibrational energy than the non-PBF cases (cf. Table 2), a difference that in this analysis follows from the larger mean photon energy of the non-PBF cases of 2.41 eV as compared to 2.28 eV of the PBF cases, also visible in Fig.3.

Whereas the photon-average method relies on the integrated OES (2), the PEAKS method is based on the spectral peaks of the OES. We take for each excited state level $v' = 0 - 9$ two allowed transitions $v' \rightarrow v''$ defined by the two largest FC factors. The energies of the v' and v'' levels are given in Tables II and IX of [30], respectively, and the emitted photon energy is the difference between these energies. If a peak in the OES falls within 20 meV distance from this photon energy, we associate the peak with that transition. We wave then the emission intensity for each peak that we associate with the occupation of the vibrational levels v' and v'' of the transition. In Fig.4 are shown the found peaks, their energies (vertical axis) and their normalized optical intensities $\hat{\Phi}$ (color code) for one (a) PBF and (b) non-PBF case. The other PBF and non-PBF cases have figures similar to these two. As one can see, up to energies up to about 2.5 eV the most probable transitions are also detected in the OES. Between 2.5 eV and about 3.2 eV the spectral peaks are not distinct enough for a clear detection. The vertical transition from the fundamental $v' = 0$ to $v'' = 8$ can be seen in both PBF and non-PBF cases. However, their normalized intensity is very low $\hat{\Phi} < 0.1$. Taking the average over the normalized intensities for the two groups of plasmas, and by assuming that $\hat{\Phi}$ is directly proportional to the population of the state, we can

(a) Excited state v' .

(b) Ground state v'' .

Fig. 5. Occupation of vibrational states. a) Excited state v' , b) ground state v'' . Red circles: PBF; blue squares: Non-PBF. The inserts show the Non-PBF spectra shifted by $v' + 1$ and $v'' + 2$.

construct the state occupation functions $P(v')$ and $P(v'')$ for PBF and non-PBF plasmas as shown in Fig.5. In this regards, we note that both vibrational state distributions do not follow the Boltzmann distribution $\sim \text{Exp}[-v'' \hbar c w_e'' / (k T_v)]$. The Boltzmann would give a maximum at $v'' = 0$. These deviations from the Boltzmann distribution are probably largely due to vibrational pumping in both cases. With this second method, we can improve the determination of the mean vibrational energy for the ground state molecules as

$$E_V = \frac{\sum_i E_{v''} P(v'')}{\sum_i P(v'')} \quad (3)$$

where again the energies $E_{v''}$ are given in Table IX of [30]. Note that, as shown in the inserts, the PBF and non-PBF cases have the same state distribution, the only difference being a shift to higher vibrational levels for the PBF cases. The mean vibration energies obtained with the two methods are summarized in Table 2. Both methods give similar results, the largest difference being 0.05 eV for the PBF cases. In the last column is the shift from non-PBF to PBF cases. Both methods

predict higher E_V for PBF cases, by 0.16 eV and 0.09 eV.

Table 2. Obtained mean vibrational energies.

Method	PBF (T_V)	Non-PBF (T'_V)	Shift ($\Delta T_V = T_V - T'_V$)
Photon-average	1.97 eV	1.81 eV	0.16 eV
PEAKS	1.92 eV	1.83 eV	0.09 eV

2.3. Vibrational temperature

On the one hand, the mean vibrational energy is in LTE a function of the temperature determined by quantum mechanics (see for example [6]). Indeed, we have then the following caloric equation of state ¹

$$E_{Ve} = \frac{T_0}{e^{T_0/T} - 1}, \quad (4)$$

where T_0 is a characteristic temperature determined by the fundamental vibrational frequency of the molecule

$$T_0 = h_P \cdot w''_e, \quad (5)$$

with h_P is the Planck constant and w''_e the first spectroscopic constant of the ground state. Spectroscopy has provided, for diatomic sulfur, $w''_e = 727.848 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (cf. Table I in [30]), in consistency with the zero-point energy of vibrations given in [32], 0.089 eV. By eq. (5), this value yields $T_0 = 1047 \text{ K}$. At high temperature $T \gg T_0$, eq. (4) can be simplified to, [33] p. 109,

$$E_{Ve} = T, \quad (6)$$

giving hence the value of 1 to the adimensional molar heat capacity due to the vibrational degrees of freedom, as a good approximation,

$$C_V \approx 1. \quad (7)$$

On the other hand, we use for the non-equilibrium temperatures the definition of the Extended Thermodynamics (ET) [34]. Thus, the vibrational temperature is generalized as the T_V value of the temperature that would give the actual vibrational mean energy E_V using the caloric equations of state, thus eq. (4) as it is vibrational energy. At high temperatures $T \gg T_0$, we have from eq. (6)

$$E_V = T_V. \quad (8)$$

Note that the ET definition of the vibrational temperature does not require any assumptions about the distribution of states in these degrees of freedom, no Boltzmann distribution in particular. It is therefore appropriate to treat our experimental results (cf. Sect. 2.2).

¹The temperatures are homogeneous to the energy in order to lighten the literal writings.

2.4. Measurement of the energy storage in the plasma

The internal energy in the plasma per unit mass due to the emitted photon gas can be calculated from the 'radiative cooling' model as follows

$$e_{h\nu} = \frac{\Phi^\dagger}{\rho} \frac{1}{S c_0}, \quad (9)$$

where Φ^\dagger is the radiation power of the plasma (optical emission), which is emitted in the optical domain, S is the area of the plasma ball ($S = \pi a_B^2$ [2]) and c_0 is the speed of light in vacuum. On the other hand, the additional energy stored in the plasma compared to the internal energy of the gas at the periphery is, since these media are distinguished according to the luminosity,

$$e - e_s = \frac{\Phi^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V V_B} \tau_{ra}, \quad (10)$$

with e and e_s the internal energy per unit mass respectively in the plasma and in the peripheral zone, τ_{ra} the characteristic decay time of the optical emission during tests of long interruptions of the power supply, of several acoustic periods, and $\zeta_V = V/V_B$ designating the volume fraction of the plasma ($\zeta_V = 1/8$ when the PBF occurs). Analysis of the decrease in light emission at long power interruption tests shows that $\tau_{ra} \approx 9 \text{ ms}$ whether or not PBF occurs [21].

Taking into account both energies yields

$$\Delta e = \frac{\Phi^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V V_B} \left(\tau_{ra} + \frac{3 a_B}{4 c_0} \right), \quad (11)$$

Obviously $\frac{3 a_B}{4 c_0} \ll \tau_{ra}$, hence (11) is simplified as follows

$$\Delta e = \frac{\Phi^\dagger \tau_{ra}}{\rho \zeta_V V_B}. \quad (12)$$

The table 3 shows the measurements we obtained with our experiments in which the bulb has a volume of $V_B = 15.6 \text{ cm}^3$. Δe is only calculated when the PBF occurs, as ζ_V is then measured at 1/8, whereas no measurement is available otherwise. Moreover, the density of the plasma being neither measured, we assume here $\rho = \rho_B = 1.816 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ even in the non-PBF case.

3. THERMODYNAMIC NON-EQUILIBRIUM PLASMA CONFINEMENT MODEL

3.1. Lumped-node model

The ideal gas model is valid in modeling the plasma lamp since the pressure in the bulb is far from condensation [35,

²Note that a_B is the radius of the bulb, i.e. the diameter of the plasma ball.

Table 3. Measurements with our experiments (Δe is calculated in assuming $\rho = \rho_B = 1.816 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$)

PBF occurs?	P_{mg} W	P_{el} W	Φ^\dagger W	$\Phi^\dagger \tau_{ra}$ J	Δe kJ/kg
yes	900	630	108	0.97	274
yes	881	617	115	1.03	291
yes	839	587	117	1.06	299
yes	853	597	111	1.00	282
no	751	526	203	1.82	

21], far below 182.1 bar, which is the critical pressure of sulfur vapor [36] :

$$p \zeta_V V_B = N T , \quad (13)$$

with T the temperature due to the degrees of freedom of the molecules exhibiting a relaxation time much shorter than the acoustic period ($\approx 30 \mu s$), so mainly the rota-translational degrees, N the number of atoms, molecules, and ions, in the plasma, p the average pressure in the plasma and $\zeta_V V_B$ the volume occupied by the plasma, as ζ_V denotes the volume fraction of the plasma (1/8 when BPF occurs) and V_B the inside volume of the bulb.

Consistency of the lumped-node model with continuum mechanics is ensured as follows. Let us consider a particle of fluid or fluid element, that has an infinitesimal mass ρdV large enough to contain millions of molecules so that the fluid can be considered as a continuous medium,

$$p(\vec{r}) = \rho(\vec{r}) \frac{T(\vec{r})}{M(\vec{r})} , \quad (14)$$

with \vec{r} the position of the particle in the laboratory frame, and $T(\vec{r})$, $\rho(\vec{r})$, and $M(\vec{r})$, its temperature³, mass density, and number average molecular mass, respectively. In a lumped-node model, the average mass density value assigned to a node is of course its mass-to-volume ratio, in order to satisfy the conservation of mass,

$$\rho = m/V . \quad (15)$$

Furthermore, the assigned pressure is the volume-averaged value in order to conserve energy

$$\int_V p(\vec{r}) dV = p V = p \zeta_V V_B . \quad (16)$$

Integration of eq. (14) on the volume of the node therefore gives

$$p V = \int_V \rho(\vec{r}) \frac{T(\vec{r})}{M(\vec{r})} dV . \quad (17)$$

³As mentioned before, the Boltzmann constant is omitted to simplify the writing; molecular heats are therefore adimensional.

Hence, noting the average molecular mass $M = m/N$, the assigned temperature T is

$$T = \frac{M}{\rho V} \int_V \frac{\rho(\vec{r})}{M(\vec{r})} T(\vec{r}) dV , \quad (18)$$

so that the ideal gas law is satisfied at each node in all cases

$$T/M = p/\rho . \quad (19)$$

3.2. Thermodynamic non-equilibrium model of the plasma

Assuming that the plasma is subject only to sufficiently fast processes that its degree of dissociation is constant, so that M is constant, we also have, from eq. (19)

$$dT/M = d(p/\rho) . \quad (20)$$

Considering furthermore a polyatomic gas with constant specific heats, the enthalpy differential per unit mass for a gas particle in non-equilibrium thermodynamics is according to [4]

$$dh = (C_F + 1) dT/M + C_S dT_S/M , \quad (21)$$

where T_S is the average energy per molecule stored in the internal degree of freedom exhibiting a relaxation time at least as large as the acoustic period. According to this relaxation criterion, we decompose the isochoric molar heat capacity as follows:

$$C = C_F + C_S , \quad (22)$$

where

- $C_F = C_{T,R} + \xi C_V$ for the degrees of *fast* relaxation, i.e. the energy stored in the translation and the rotation degrees, $C_{T,R} \approx 5/2$, plus the vibrational energy of the molecules lying in the upper levels of the vibrational ladder,
- $C_S = (1 - \xi) \cdot C_V$ for degrees *slow* relaxation, i.e., the remaining vibrational energy.

The parameter ξ is indeed the fraction of diatomic molecules with high vibrational excitation, for which the anharmonicity causes the vibrational relaxation time to drop [31]. We assume here that $\xi \approx 0$, i.e. that the energy stored in the highest vibrational levels is negligible compared to the vibrational energy of the whole population. Then $C_F = C_{T,R}$ as well as $C_S = C_V$, and $T_S = T_V$, the vibrational temperature. With this approximation, we have

$$de = C_{T,R} dT/M + C_V dT_V/M , \quad (23)$$

where e is the internal energy per mass unit, as well as, in accordance with eq. (21),

$$dh = (C_{T,R} + 1) dT/M + C_V dT_V/M , \quad (24)$$

where h is the enthalpy per mass unit, which leads by eq. (20) to

$$dh = (C_{T,R} + 1) d(p/\rho) + C_V dT_V/M . \quad (25)$$

We apply first this non-equilibrium model to the gas in the peripheral zone in considering that (i) the heat capacities are independent of temperature above T_0 , where the enthalpy is h_0 , and that (ii) the vibrational temperature is equal to the wall temperature T_w because of the surface vibrational relaxation, i.e. catalytic deactivation of vibrational degrees through collisions on the wall [20]

$$h_s = (C_{T,R} + 1) p_s/\rho_s + C_V T_w/M_s + h_0 . \quad (26)$$

We also apply Eq. (25) for the plasma, but taking into account the additional internal energy corresponding to the luminescence (cf. Sect. 2.4). So with Eq. (12)

$$h = (C_{T,R} + 1) p/\rho + C_V T_V/M + \frac{\tau_{ra} \Phi^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V V_B} + h_0 . \quad (27)$$

Since the plasma and the surrounding gas do not have the same chemical composition, their specific heat capacities may be different. However, both are dominated by diatomic sulfur. So in a first approach, we assume that they have exactly the same specific heat capacities. In this model, the enthalpy difference between the two nodes (cf. Fig.6) is hence

$$h - h_s = (1 + C_{T,R}) \left(\frac{p}{\rho} - \frac{p_s}{\rho_s} \right) + C_V \left(\frac{T_V}{M} - \frac{T_w}{M_s} \right) + \frac{\tau_{ra} \Phi^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V V_B} . \quad (28)$$

Fig. 6. Change in the properties of the medium when crossing the boundary between the plasma and the surrounding gas (peripheral node): enthalpy per mass unit $h - h_s$, pressure $p - p_s$, vibrational temperature $T_V - T_w$, mass density $\rho - \rho_s$, and molar mass $M - M_s$.

When the PBF occurs, $\zeta_V = 1/8$ and the densities are equal $\rho = \rho_s$ since the ball remains in the middle of the bulb; these densities are therefore also both equal to the average

density in the bulb ρ_B , which is a given (cf. [37]). Thus

$$h - h_s = (1 + C_{T,R}) \left(\frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} \right) + C_V \left(\frac{T_V}{M} - \frac{T_w}{M_s} \right) + \frac{8 \tau_{ra} \Phi^\dagger}{\rho_B V_B} . \quad (29)$$

with $\Delta p = p - p_s$, the pressure jump that confines the plasma when the PBF occurs. On the other hand, if no PBF occurs, there is no confining force. In this case, the pressure is balanced $\Delta p = 0$ in the coarse time scale. So eq. (28) gives this time, assuming moreover that the wall temperature as well as the temperature at the periphery (surrounding gas) are not significantly affected because of the wall thermal inertia,

$$h' - h_s = (1 + C_{T,R}) p'_B \frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_s \rho} + C_V \left(\frac{T'_V}{M} - \frac{T_w}{M_s} \right) + \frac{\tau_{ra} \Phi'^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V V_B} , \quad (30)$$

with p'_B the average pressure in the bulb when no-PBF occurs. During the phase change, the transfer of a gas particle from the periphery to the plasma is reversible at the plasma boundary. Thus, under this condition with in addition $p'_B \approx p_B$, considering micro-fluctuations in the subacoustic time scale, the stationary isobaric process gives

$$h' - h_s = q_{rev} , \quad (31)$$

with q_{rev} the reversible heat exchange. On the other hand, an additional work $\Delta p/\rho_B$ is necessary when the PBF occurs, for a fluid particle to cross the boundary between the plasma and the surrounding gas due to the force that confines the plasma. Thus, at the phase change, the stationary isochoric process gives

$$h - h_s = q_{rev} + \Delta p/\rho_B . \quad (32)$$

Hence, from eq. (31) and (32)

$$h - h' = \Delta p/\rho_B , \quad (33)$$

and comparing moreover eq. (30) and (29) yields

$$\frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} = C_V \frac{T_V - T'_V}{M} + \frac{\tau_{ra}}{V_B} \left(\frac{8 \Phi^\dagger}{\rho_B} - \frac{\Phi'^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V} \right) + (1 + C_{T,R}) \left(\frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} - p_B \frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_s \rho} \right) , \quad (34)$$

which gives (cf. Appendix 7.2.2)

$$C_{T,R} \frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} = (1 + C_{T,R}) p_B \frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_s \rho} - C_V \frac{T_V - T'_V}{M} - \frac{\tau_{ra}}{V_B} \left(\frac{8 \Phi^\dagger}{\rho_B} - \frac{\Phi'^\dagger}{\rho \zeta_V} \right) . \quad (35)$$

Note also that it takes a few seconds for the luminous flux to change (see Figure 1 of [38]), so presumably the rightmost terms in eq. (35) is negligible

$$\Delta p \approx \rho_B \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} p_B \frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_s \rho} - \rho_B \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{T_V - T'_V}{M} . \quad (36)$$

Noting that $\rho_s \rho \approx \rho_B^2$ and denoting the vibrational temperature shift $\Delta T_V = T_V - T'_V$, a measured parameter (cf. Table 2), we obtain

$$\Delta p \approx \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} p_B \frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_B} - \rho_B \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\Delta T_V}{M} . \quad (37)$$

Moreover, the application of eq. (19) to the whole bulb gives

$$\frac{T_B}{M_B} = \frac{p_B}{\rho_B} , \quad (38)$$

where the index B denotes the average over the entire content. The relative pressure jump is thus

$$\frac{\Delta p}{p_B} = \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_B} - \frac{M_B}{M} \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\Delta T_V}{T_B} . \quad (39)$$

Substituting further the mass fraction as derived in Appendix 7.2.2, eq. (63), we obtain

$$\frac{\Delta p}{p_B} = \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\rho_s / \rho_B - 1}{\zeta_V} - \frac{M_B}{M} \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\Delta T_V}{T_B} . \quad (40)$$

Furthermore, assuming that the mass of the plasma does not change during the phase transition (cf. Appendix 7.2.4), it follows from eq. (82)

$$\frac{\Delta p}{p_B} = \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\zeta_V - 1/8}{\zeta_V (1 - \zeta_V)} - \frac{M_B}{M} \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\Delta T_V}{T_B} . \quad (41)$$

Alternatively, eq. (41) can be recast using the relative variation of the volume fraction of the plasma $\delta\zeta_V = 8\zeta_V - 1$ using eq. (73)

$$\frac{\Delta p}{p_B} = \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} \frac{8\delta\zeta_V}{(1 + \delta\zeta_V)(7 - \delta\zeta_V)} - \frac{M_B}{M} \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\Delta T_V}{T_B} . \quad (42)$$

Further assuming $M_B \approx M$, this result is simplified to

$$\frac{\Delta p}{p_B} \approx \frac{1 + C_{T,R}}{C_{T,R}} \frac{8\delta\zeta_V}{(1 + \delta\zeta_V)(7 - \delta\zeta_V)} - \frac{C_V}{C_{T,R}} \frac{\Delta T_V}{T_B} , \quad (43)$$

and represented in Fig. 7, as a function of the relative variation of the plasma volume fraction $\delta\zeta_V$. In addition, assuming the transition is quasi-isothermal we estimate (cf. Appendix 7.2.2) that $\delta\zeta_V \in [1.8; 2.3]$ (cf. Fig. 12). Thus, by zooming in on this interval (cf. Fig. 8), we observe that the pressure jump would then be of the order of 5 to 8 bars since $p_B = 5.23 \text{ bar}$ (cf. Table 1). The pressure jump is thus clearly significant.

Fig. 7. Relative pressure jump $\Delta p/p_B$ between the plasma ball and the peripheral zone versus the relative variation of the volume fraction of the plasma $\delta\zeta_V$, calculated with eq. (43) for the two measured values of vibrational temperature shift ΔT_V obtained with the methods 'Photon average' and 'PEAKS' (cf. Sect. 2.2, Table 2).

Fig. 8. Zoom of Fig. 7.

In Fig.9, left, the pressure of the plasma and the periphery are shown as a function of the relative pressure jump. The plasma pressure increase is much steeper than the peripheral pressure decrease due to the volume fraction of 1/8 of the PBF. The plasma volume fraction ζ_V before the transition is shown on the right together with the compress ratio $(1/8)/\zeta_V$.

4. SURFACE VIBRATIONAL RELAXATION TIME

Thanks to the in-depth analysis of the shape of the PBF described in Sect. 2.1, we have come to the conclusion that a two-cells structure appears when the PBF occurs. As a result of this dissipative structure, heat transfer from the plasma to the bulb wall is enhanced (cf. Fig. 4 of [23]) and dominated by free convection. Using this feature, we determine the dynamic characteristics of surface catalytic deactivation by developing a thermodynamic non-equilibrium model of the whole bulb.

Fig. 9. Left: The plasma (blue) and periphery (red) pressure as a function of the relative pressure jump $\Delta p/p_B$. Right: The plasma volume ratio before the transition to the PBF phase ζ_V (blue) and the compression ratio, i.e., the plasma volume fraction in the PBF phase divided by ζ_V (red), both as a function of the relative variation of the volume fraction $\delta\zeta_V$. For example, if $\delta\zeta_V = 2$ the volume fraction before the transition ζ_V is 0.375, then the compression ratio is 1/3, which means that the volume of the plasma before the transition would have been triple the volume of the PBF ($V_B/8$).

4.1. Thermodynamic non-equilibrium model of the bulb

From the energy flow diagram developed to model free convection (cf. Appendix 7.3.1, Fig. 14), we adopt for the plasma bulb the diagram shown in Fig. 10, where four thermal sources are involved. Indeed the heat source is plasma, but it is divided into two sources because of the discrepancy between the vibrational temperature for the slow degrees of freedom of the molecules and the rota-translational temperature for the fast degrees⁴, according to the non-equilibrium model given in Sect. 3:

- The heat source at the vibrational temperature T_V .
- The heat source at the temperature T .
- The wall of the bulb is an intermediate heat sink, at temper-

⁴The rota-translational temperature is simply called “temperature”.

ature T_w .

- The ambient environment is the ultimate heat sink, at room temperature T_r .

The radiative heat transfer model is broken down into two parts, microwave heating on the one hand and radiative cooling on the other.

4.1.1. Microwave heating

The plasma is heated by the microwave power source, a 2.45 GHz magnetron. We measure the electromagnetic energy P_{el} dissipated in the lamp, i.e. in the plasma, as a good approximation. Assuming that the mass of the plasma is the same whether the PBF occurs or not (cf. Appendix 7.2.4), the heat input per unit mass of plasma is

$$\dot{q}_e^\downarrow = \frac{8 P_{el}}{\rho_B V_B}. \quad (44)$$

Our optical emission spectrum (OES) analysis (cf. Sect. 2.2) shows clearly that the vibrational temperature is much larger than any expected value for the temperature $T_V \gg T$ (cf. Table 2), whether PBF occurs or not. In addition, the vibrational excitation of polyatomic molecules promotes the release of electrons through stepwise ionization; there is a strong increase of the electron energy distribution function as well as ionization and electronic excitation rate coefficients with vibrational temperature [39], p.185–186. Furthermore, the higher the excitation of the molecule, the larger its cross section of inelastic electron collisions. Indeed, citing R. Celiberto et al. [40]:

- the threshold for an inelastic process involving a vibrationally excited molecule decreases with increasing vibrational excitation of the molecule, and
- the cross section of the process increases (for some processes dramatically) with the increase of vibrational excitation of the molecule.

It is also noted by Cascella et al. [41] that: “In the excitation processes that play an important role in modeling molecular plasmas, the presence of ‘hot’ molecules and multiple quantum excitations has been shown to be important in simpler diatoms such as H_2 , N_2 , and O_2 ”. So it is likely that the same is true in our case, as S_2 is the main component of the plasma. We therefore consider that most of the absorbed microwave power is coupled first to the heat source at the vibrational temperature T_V , as in the diagram in Fig. 10. Note that two thermal reservoirs are needed to generate free convection (cf. Appendix 7.3.1). Therefore, the loop inside the plasma results only from the diffusion of momentum from the peripheral zone into the plasma. This is illustrated in Fig. 10 by a backward flux of work which is dissipated into the heat source of temperature T , the rota-translational temperature of the plasma.

4.1.2. Radiative cooling

The plasma is also directly coupled to the ambient environment by radiative cooling, since the glass is transparent in the optical spectral range. Although continuous, the OES we obtained experimentally (cf. Sect. 2.2) differ significantly from Planck's law (black body); hence the optical radiant flux Φ^\uparrow cannot be considered as a heat flux. However, it is neither composed of true spectral lines, as seen in Sect. 2.2, in particular because of the pressure broadening effect [39], p. 424. Therefore, Φ^\uparrow is considered a work flow for one part, \dot{w}'_o per unit mass of plasma, and a heat flow for the other part, \dot{q}'_o also per unit mass of plasma,

$$\frac{8\Phi^\uparrow}{\rho_B V_B} = \dot{q}'_o + \dot{w}'_o = g_a \cdot (\dot{q}'_o + \dot{w}'_o)^\uparrow, \quad (45)$$

where g_a is the attenuation factor due to the glass wall ($0 < g_a < 1$). The radiation passing through the glass, Φ^\uparrow , is among the available measurements, as well as the volume of the bulb V_B and the average mass density of the contents ρ_B , the rate of energy consumption per unit mass of plasma \dot{q}'_e , via eq. (44), and the temperature on the bulb T_w . As also shown in the diagram in Fig. 10, the wall of the bulb is cooled by heat transfer to the environment by thermal radiation \dot{q}'_{ir} as well as by conduction and convection processes \dot{q}'_{ce} .

Regarding the flux transmitted through the glass, the reflections on the interfaces are neglected since most of the incident rays are far from tangential. Hence, we derive the optical transmittance t_o from Kirchoff's law

$$t_o = 1 - \epsilon_o, \quad (46)$$

with ϵ_o the emissivity of the glass in the optical domain, which is close to zero unlike its value in the far infrared domain (beyond $5 \mu m$), cf. [42] p. 217. At normal temperature, the attenuation per unit length in the glass is less than 10 dB/km . Hence, $g_{a \text{ dB}} \approx 10 \text{ dB/km} \cdot 1.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ km} = 15 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ dB}$, as thickness of the bulb wall is 1.5 mm , giving $g_a \approx 10^{15 \cdot 10^{-7}}$, a quantity very close to unity. We assume hence that $g_a = 1$.

4.2. Characteristic time of surface vibration relaxation

Regarding non radiative cooling, the plasma is coupled to the bulb wall by conduction and free convection in the peripheral region. The heat source is at vibrational temperature T_V , since whole the power inflow is assumed to pass by the vibrational reservoir according to the arguments given in Sect. 4.1.1. On the other hand, the cooling could take two paths, as shown in Fig. 10, either the heat of vibrational relaxation is first transfer to the rota-translational internal degrees of freedom of the gas or it is directly absorbed by the wall of the bulb, the intermediate heat sink of temperature T_w . It is indeed known that catalytic deactivation of vibrational degrees may occur through collisions and recombinations on the wall

Fig. 10. Thermodynamic diagram of the plasma bulb. $\eta_{cw} = 1 - T_w/T_V$; $\eta_{cr} = 1 - T_r/T_w$; $P_{el} = \dot{q}'_e = \dot{q}'_{rad} + \dot{q}'_h + \dot{q}'_h \approx \dot{q}'_{rad} + \dot{q}'_h$ and $\dot{q}'_{rad} = 8(P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow/g_a)/(\rho_B V_B)$.

[20]. We observe in the photographs of the PBF presented in Fig. 16 that the plasma entrained in the convection cell chimney, in the peripheral zone, briefly quenches along the bulb wall. Noting moreover that when the PBF occurs, the periphery must be significantly colder than the plasma ball because of the recirculations due to the convective cells (cf. Fig. 2), one can assume that the gas in the periphery is then vibrationally *frozen*. Vibrational relaxation is therefore largely dominated by deactivation on the wall, with a much shorter characteristic time τ_V^* than if the relaxation took place in the bulk of the peripheral zone. The eq. (121) of Appendix 7.4, which gives the production of entropy due to vibrational relaxation, is thus rewritten by substituting the characteristic time by $\tau_V \rightarrow \tau_V^*$ and the temperature by $T \rightarrow T_w$, since the heat sink is the wall in this case,

$$\dot{s}_p = \frac{C_V}{M \tau_V^*} \frac{(T_V - T_w)^2}{T_w T_V}. \quad (47)$$

Moreover, we have from eq. (44) and the energy flow (see diagram in Fig. 10), neglecting \dot{q}'_h

$$\dot{q}'_h \approx \dot{q}'_e - \dot{q}'_{rad} \approx \frac{8}{\rho_B V_B} (P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow). \quad (48)$$

Applying the result of Appendix. 7.3.1, i.e. substituting in eq. (101) $T_h \rightarrow T_V$ for the heat source and $T_c \rightarrow T_w$ for the heat

sink as well as $q_s^\uparrow \rightarrow q_{ws}^\uparrow$ for the heat to be absorbed by the wall and $\eta_C \rightarrow \eta_{cw}$ for the Carnot efficiency, we obtain

$$\dot{q}_{ws}^\uparrow = \eta_{cw} \dot{q}_h^\downarrow \approx \left(1 - \frac{T_w}{T_V}\right) \frac{8}{\rho_B V_B} (P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow) . \quad (49)$$

Noting furthermore that $T_V \gg T_w$, as shown from the our analysis to the OES measurements (cf. Sect. 2.2, Table 2), we can simplify this equation to

$$\dot{q}_{ws}^\uparrow \approx 8 \frac{P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow}{\rho_B V_B} . \quad (50)$$

as well as eq. (47) to

$$\dot{s}_p \approx \frac{C_V}{M} \frac{T_V}{\tau_V^*} \frac{T_V}{T_w} . \quad (51)$$

Assuming further that vibrational relaxation largely dominates any dissipation when PBF occurs, as this is the mechanism that produces the confining pressure according to the non-equilibrium model of the plasma (cf. Sect. 3.2), we have from the two last equations

$$\frac{8}{\rho_B V_B} (P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow) \approx T_w \dot{s}_p \approx \frac{C_V}{M} \frac{T_V}{\tau_V^*} T_V , \quad (52)$$

giving a way to estimate the characteristic time of surface vibrational relaxation

$$\tau_V^* \approx \frac{C_V T_V}{M} \frac{\rho_B V_B}{8(P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow)} . \quad (53)$$

Moreover, we introduce the total number of molecules and ions in the whole bulb $N_B = \rho_B V_B / M_B$ by the ideal gas law (eq. (38))

$$\tau_V^* \approx C_V T_V \frac{M_B}{M} \frac{N_B}{8(P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow)} . \quad (54)$$

Assuming that $M_B = M$ in first approach, since S_2 is the main component of the plasma as long as the degree of dissociation is low, as well as $C_V = 1$ (cf. eq. (7), Sect. 2.3)

$$\tau_V^* \approx \frac{T_V p_B V_B}{8 T_B (P_{el} - \Phi^\uparrow)} . \quad (55)$$

The results obtained from the two values of the vibrational temperature (cf. Table 2), measured with the two methods described in Sect. 2.2, have a low variability (cf. Table 4): the standard deviation is less than 1 ms in both cases as well as for the joint series. The results are all close to 21 ms. Note that this value is much larger than the measurement given in [21], $\tau_V \approx 15 \mu s$. In fact, this is not an inconsistency because this characteristic time is related to the vibrational relaxation in the plasma ball. In addition, the current modeling assumes that the vibrational relaxation is much faster at the wall compared to the interior of the peripheral zone volume, but not

compared to the plasma interior. The assumption of a vibrationally *frozen* gas in the periphery actually follows from the former modeling [21]. We therefore have the following ordering of the vibrational relaxation times in the three regions, with the current estimation indicated in the parenthesis

$$\text{plasma } (15 \mu s) \ll \text{wall } (20 \text{ ms}) \ll \text{peripheral gas } (\rightarrow \infty) . \quad (56)$$

In addition, as can be seen in the photographs in Figure 16, the plasma chimney extends along the wall of the bulb for an arc length of about 8 mm. The velocity of the gas particles in the outer part of the convection cell could therefore have a magnitude on the order of 0.4 m/s, considered in the coarse time-scale modeling (ignoring acoustic displacement and other faster movements).

Table 4. Characteristic time of surface vibration relaxation calculated according to eq. (55) taking the characteristics published in [21] $\rho_B = 1.816 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$; $p_B = 5.23 \text{ bar}$; $V_B = 15.6 \text{ cm}^3$ and, in the upper part, $T_V = 1.97 \text{ eV}$ (obtained with the 'Photon average' method, cf. Table 2) as well as, in the lower part, $T_V = 1.92 \text{ eV}$ (obtained with the 'PEAKS' method, cf. Table 2).

T_V	P_{el}	Φ^\uparrow	τ_V^*
eV	W	W	ms
1.97	630	108	20.3
1.97	617	115	21.1
1.97	587	117	22.5
1.97	597	111	21.8
1.92	630	108	19.8
1.92	617	115	21.0
1.92	587	117	22.0
1.92	597	111	21.2

5. CONCLUSIONS

Our experimental setup, originally designed as an electrodeless sulfur plasma lamp, can produce molecular plasmas, especially diatomic ones, that are far from local thermodynamic equilibrium (non-LTE). We have shown that these plasmas have high internal energy due to the occupation of high-order vibrational levels, the distribution of states being far from Boltzmann, Fig. 5, and that these levels are even higher when the PBF occurs. In addition, the plasma has a high internal energy due to dissociated S_2 that release heat in recombination processes. Plasmas produced in an atmospheric hypersonic

shock wave share both of these characteristics. Essentially, our device constitutes of three components that have analogous regions in an atmospheric reentry as follows:

- S₂-S mixture plasma - Shock wave
- Peripheral gas - Shock layer
- Bulb wall - Vehicle wall

Therefore, we believe that our facility could be of interest to ESA to provide a physical basis for the development of a new type of laboratory device for the prediction of the thermal load of the reentry vehicle protection systems.

Moreover, the theoretical part of this work improves the physical understanding of the PBF confinement by extending our previous model to a three-node (plasma, peripheral gas, wall) lumped model and to account for the non-LTE effects. By considering the enthalpy difference between the plasma and the peripheral gas when the PBF 1) occurs and 2) does not occur (non-confining), using the fact that the PBF occupies 1/8 of the bulb volume, and by subtracting these two differences, eliminates the contribution due to the reversible heat exchange and leads to the expression for the pressure jump over the plasma boundary without which the PBF could not occur. Using the measured vibrational temperatures (Sect.2) and after certain simplifications, the pressure jump across the PBF boundary can be expressed as (43), Fig.7. The predicted pressure jump is of the order of a few bars, which is significant compared to the average pressure in the bulb.

We assume that all the input power is absorbed by the vibrational modes of the plasma molecules, in agreement with the literature. Since the peripheral gas needs to be significantly colder than the plasma in order for the supposed convective cell structure, Fig.2, to exist, one can assume that the peripheral gas is vibrationally frozen. Thereby, the vibrational relaxation process is largely dominated by the deactivation on the bulb wall, a purely surface relaxation process. Considering the plasma - peripheral gas - wall as a heat engine with the hot temperature being at the plasma vibrational temperature and the cold temperature at the wall allows us to use the Carnot efficiency for the dissipation, because steady free convection does not provide any work. When the PBF occurs, the surface relaxation largely dominates any other dissipation mechanism, consistent with the assumptions made above in the non-LTE model for the pressure jump. We then find for the vibrational relaxation time at the surface the expression (55), which gives about 20 ms with the measured vibrational and bulb temperatures. As the chimney extends to about 8 mm distance on the wall, Figs.1(b) and 16, we can estimate the velocity of the gas particles to be about 0.4 m/s at the wall, which is comparable to the values of about 1 to 2 m/s found in [17], p. 351, for the recombination-rate coefficient of oxygen atoms at the wall of the STS-2 shuttle during a reentry flight into Earth's atmosphere. This parameter could not be measured directly, but only deduced from the comparison of calculated and measured heat fluxes. Our microwave device could therefore bring progress in this metrology challenge.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank the European Space Agency for a support of our work with funding (contract ESA RFP/3-17148/21/NL/GLC/ov). Our thank goes also to the company Lumartix, who has provided specific components of the prototype, like the light bulbs and the microwave applicator. The authors are also grateful to the group of Prof. Seth Putterman, an expert in sonoluminescence and dense plasma at the University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA), for scientific exchanges.

7. ANNEX

7.1. Bulb wall temperature

The bulb wall temperature was monitored with an infrared camera by Prof. Putterman's group at the University of California (UCLA), who reproduced the PBF phenomenon with a setup similar to ours. It appears that the bulb has thermal periodicity of around 200 s (cf. Fig. 4 in [23]). As reported in this publication, the bulb heats up when the plasma enters the trapped state (PBF). When the temperature rise reaches about 100 K, the plasma returns to the normal state, which reduces the heat transfer to the bulb. When the glass has cooled down to its initial temperature, the plasma ball reappears, and so on. By taking a value of 0.65 for the emissivity of quartz at 1300 K, they obtained a temperature of about 1290 K on average; this is the value used here when there is no other specification.

7.2. Energy balance at extinction

If a plasma goes out, its change in energy can be assessed from measurements of the drop in emissions during power interruption tests

$$q_{ra}^\uparrow = \Phi^\uparrow \tau_{ra} , \quad (57)$$

where Φ^\uparrow is the radiation power of the plasma, which is emitted in the optical domain and τ_{ra} is the decay time characteristic of the emission decline : $\tau_{ra} \approx 9 \text{ ms}$ [21]. This is what happens to a fluid particle that stops being luminescent, like along the streamline 2 → 3 (cf. Fig. 11). For a fluid particle that passes from the periphery to the plasma, the balance is given by the energy stored in plasma in add to the internal energy of the gas in the periphery, since these states distinguish themselves by the luminescence

$$e - e_s = \frac{\Phi^\uparrow}{\rho} \frac{\tau_{ra}}{V_B/8} , \quad (58)$$

Moreover, the peripheral zone is assumed to be filled with a diatomic ideal gas of *frozen* vibrational degrees, therefore

$$de - \frac{5}{2} \frac{dT_s}{M_s} = 8 \frac{\tau_{ra} d\Phi^\uparrow}{\rho V_B} . \quad (59)$$

Hence, eq. (23) gives

$$8 \frac{\tau_{ra} d\Phi^\dagger}{\rho V_B} = \frac{C_{T,R} dp}{\rho} + \frac{C_V dT_V}{M} + \frac{5 dT_s}{2 M_s} , \quad (60)$$

Fig. 11. Streamlines in the plasma sheath and in the peripheral zone with the main dissipation, due to vibrational relaxation (cf. Sect. 4).

7.2.1. Conservation of mass

By designating $\zeta_V = V/V_B$ the ratio between the volume taken by the plasma and the total volume inside the bulb ($\zeta_V = 1/8$ when the PBF occurs), the conservation of mass gives in any case

$$\zeta_V \rho + (1 - \zeta_V) \rho_s = \rho_B , \quad (61)$$

which yields

$$\zeta_V = \frac{\rho_s - \rho_B}{\rho_s - \rho} = \frac{1 - \rho_B/\rho_s}{1 - \rho/\rho_s} . \quad (62)$$

So we can derive the following mass fraction

$$\frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_B} = \frac{\rho_s - \rho_B}{\zeta_V \rho_B} = \frac{\rho_s/\rho_B - 1}{\zeta_V} . \quad (63)$$

Also from eq. (62), we have

$$\zeta_V - \zeta_V \frac{\rho}{\rho_B} \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s} = 1 - \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s} , \quad (64)$$

i.e.

$$\zeta_V - 1 = \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s} \left(\zeta_V \frac{\rho}{\rho_B} - 1 \right) . \quad (65)$$

So we obtain

$$\frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s} = \frac{\zeta_V - 1}{\zeta_V \rho/\rho_B - 1} , \quad (66)$$

which yields via eq. (67)

$$\frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s} = 1 - \delta\zeta_V/7 . \quad (67)$$

7.2.2. No PBF occurring

In the Non-PBF cases, the pressure in the bulb is uniform in the coarse time scale modeling. Using the ideal gas law (eq. (19)), it comes

$$\frac{\rho_s T'_s}{M'_s} = \frac{\rho T'}{M'} = \frac{\rho_B T'_B}{M'_B} , \quad (68)$$

which yields

$$\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_B} = \frac{T'_B M'_s}{T'_s M'_B} ; \quad \frac{\rho}{\rho_B} = \frac{T'_B M'}{T' M'_B} . \quad (69)$$

Noting moreover that $M'_s \approx M' \approx M'_B$, we estimate

$$\frac{T'}{T'_s} = \frac{\rho_s}{\rho} ; \quad \frac{T'_B}{T'_s} = \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_B} . \quad (70)$$

So we can derive the mass fraction of eq. (63)

$$\frac{\rho_s - \rho}{\rho_B} = \frac{\rho_s/\rho_B - 1}{\zeta_V} = \frac{T'_B/T'_s - 1}{\zeta_V} . \quad (71)$$

In addition, eq. (62) gives according to eq. (70)

$$\zeta_V = \frac{1 - \rho_B/\rho_s}{1 - \rho/\rho_s} = \frac{1 - T'_s/T'_B}{1 - T'_s/T'} . \quad (72)$$

Thus, the relative change in plasma volume fraction compared to the PBF cases is as follows

$$\delta\zeta_V = \frac{\zeta_V - 1/8}{1/8} = 8\zeta_V - 1 = 8 \frac{1 - T'_s/T'_B}{1 - T'_s/T'} - 1 . \quad (73)$$

The result of this calculation is shown in Fig. 12 as a function of plasma temperature T' taken in the expected range according to the measurements in the plasma of a similar sulfur lamp $T = 4.1 \text{ kK}$ [43]. The mean prior temperature in the bulb, T'_B , is not known, but we did a reliable measure of the mean temperature in the bulb when the PBF occurs, T_B , through the measurement of the resonance frequency [21] (cf. Table 1). We assume moreover the transition is quasi-isothermal $T'_B \approx T_B$, we have considered three values of T'_B , at 0, 1 and 2 % above T_B . From this assumption, as an estimate, it appears that $\zeta_V \in [.35; .41]$, i.e. $\delta\zeta_V \in [180; 228] \%$.

7.2.3. PBF occurring

In PBF cases, the density is assumed to be approximately equal in the plasma and in the surrounding gas because the plasma ball remains in the center of the bulb, instead of rising by buoyancy if its density were lower

$$\rho_s = \rho = \rho_B . \quad (74)$$

Fig. 12. Relative variation of the volume fraction of the plasma $\delta\zeta_V = 8\zeta_V - 1$, according to eq. (73), versus the plasma temperature T' for 3 values of the mean prior temperature in the bulb, $T'_B = 1.00 T_B$, $T'_B = 1.01 T_B$ and $T'_B = 1.02 T_B$. The temperature at the bulb wall is the average of the measurements of Koulakis et al. reported in Fig. 4, in [23] $T_w = 1290$ K, and the temperature in the surrounding gas is $T'_s = (T'_B + T_w)/2$.

But now, the pressure is not balance

$$p = p_s + \Delta p , \quad (75)$$

so that

$$\frac{p}{\rho_B} = \frac{p_s}{\rho_B} + \frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} . \quad (76)$$

and the ideal gas law (eq. (19)) gives as well

$$\frac{T}{M} = \frac{T_s}{M_s} + \frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} . \quad (77)$$

As moreover that $M \approx M_s \approx M_B$ since the diatomic sulfur is the dominant component in all the interior of the bulb, it comes

$$\frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} = \frac{T}{M} - \frac{T_s}{M_s} \approx \frac{T - T_s}{M_B} . \quad (78)$$

The plasma being hotter than the peripheral zone, according to the second law of thermodynamics, we have

$$\frac{\Delta p}{\rho_B} > 0 . \quad (79)$$

This is consistent with the previous result, from Sect. 7.2.2, saying that the plasma volume has decreased when PBF occurs.

7.2.4. Conservation of plasma mass

The PBF phase change is fast in comparison to the variation of the wall temperature as well as to the chemical reactions occurring in the plasma, producing the emitted light. We therefore assume that the contraction during the phase change does

not change the mass of the plasma

$$\rho_B V_B / 8 = \rho \zeta_V V_B , \quad (80)$$

so

$$\frac{\rho}{\rho_B} = \frac{1}{8\zeta_V} . \quad (81)$$

As we estimated $\zeta_V \in [.35; .41]$ (cf. Sect. 7.2.2), it appears therefore that $\rho/\rho_B \in [5; 7]$ %, also in the quasi-isothermal assumption.

Moreover, using eq. (66), we derive from the conservation of plasma mass that

$$\frac{\rho_B}{\rho_s} = \frac{\zeta_V - 1}{1/8 - 1} = 8(1 - \zeta_V)/7 . \quad (82)$$

Again, the quasi-isothermal estimate $\zeta_V \in [.35; .41]$ yields $\rho_B/\rho_s \in [68; 74]$ %. Furthermore, eq. (82) is recast with the relative variation of the volume fraction of the plasma $\delta\zeta_V = 8\zeta_V - 1$

$$\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_B} = \frac{\delta\zeta_V}{7 - \delta\zeta_V} + 1 . \quad (83)$$

7.3. Thermodynamic diagram

7.3.1. Steady-state one-loop free convection

Fig. 13. A real closed system in steady regime can be represented in thermodynamics by a Carnot cycle whose work is partly dissipated in an additional thermal source, of temperature T_s ; it is a heat sink for the engines but a heat source for the heat pumps.

The working fluid we consider circulates in a constant flux thermodynamic cycle, i.e. in steady state. Energy conservation gives

$$w_i^\uparrow = q_h^\downarrow - q_{c0}^\uparrow . \quad (84)$$

This quantity is positive for a heat engine (cf. Fig. 13, b), as then $q_h^\downarrow > q_{c0}^\uparrow$, meaning the flux of work is outward. In contrast, this flux is negative for a heat pump (cf. Fig. 13, a), since then $q_h^\downarrow < q_{c0}^\uparrow$, meaning this flux is inward in that case. As this cycle is reversible, its entropy production is null

$$\frac{q_{c0}^\uparrow}{T_c} - \frac{q_h^\downarrow}{T_h} = 0 , \quad (85)$$

so that the heat communicated to the cold source is given by

$$q_{c0}^\uparrow = q_h^\downarrow \frac{T_c}{T_h} . \quad (86)$$

Substitution in eq. (84) yields

$$w_i^\uparrow = q_h^\downarrow \left(1 - \frac{T_c}{T_h} \right) . \quad (87)$$

As we already know, the energy efficiency of an ideal heat engine operating according to the Carnot cycle is indeed

$$\eta_C = \frac{w_i^\uparrow}{q_h^\downarrow} = 1 - \frac{T_c}{T_h} . \quad (88)$$

This ideal cycle does not however allow modelling free convection in steady state. According to A. Bejan, indeed: "The convection loop ... is equivalent to the cycle executed by the working fluid in a heat engine. ... the heat engine cycle drives its working fluid fast enough so that its entire work output potential is dissipated by friction", [44] p. 111. Let's do a test by setting

$$\eta_C = 0 , \quad (89)$$

we would necessarily have from (88)

$$T_c = T_h , \quad (90)$$

which means no heat transfer! Note that this is actually true for all types of heat transfer (conduction, convection, radiation), some dissipation must occur. Therefore, we introduce in the model an additional virtual heat source, of temperature T_s , to absorb the dissipated work. For a general approach – not limited to free convection – a fraction of the Carnot work output, called 'work output potential' by A. Bejan, is dissipated

$$w_i^\uparrow = w^\uparrow + q_s^\uparrow , \quad (91)$$

where the heat communicated to the additional heat source q_s^\uparrow is such that the production of entropy along the real thermodynamic cycles is

$$s_p = \frac{q_s^\uparrow}{T_s} = \frac{w_i^\uparrow - w^\uparrow}{T_s} , \quad (92)$$

For a heat engine of real energy efficiency $\eta = w^\uparrow/q_h^\downarrow$, we have thus

$$s_p = \frac{q_h^\downarrow}{T_s} (\eta_C - \eta) . \quad (93)$$

Moreover, the conservation of energy gives, from eq. (84),

$$w^\uparrow = q_h^\downarrow - q_{c0}^\uparrow - q_s^\uparrow , \quad (94)$$

so

$$q_s^\uparrow = w_i^\uparrow - w^\uparrow = (\eta_C - \eta) q_h^\downarrow , \quad (95)$$

and

$$q_{c0}^\uparrow + q_s^\uparrow = q_h^\downarrow - w^\uparrow = (1 - \eta) q_h^\downarrow . \quad (96)$$

Modeling consistency requires that entropy production be conserved, so that eq. (85) must be found from eq. (92) under the condition that $q_s = 0$

$$s_p = \frac{q_{c0}^\uparrow}{T_c} + \frac{q_s^\uparrow}{T_s} - \frac{q_h^\downarrow}{T_h} , \quad (97)$$

It turns out that no additional virtual heat sink is needed, i.e. the work loss is dissipated in the heat sink of the engine

$$T_s = T_c , \quad (98)$$

since then eq. (97) and eq. (96) yield

$$s_p = q_h^\downarrow \left(\frac{1 - \eta}{T_c} - \frac{1}{T_h} \right) . \quad (99)$$

In particular, we obtain in the case of free convection – so when η is zero – that all the entire work output potential, i.e. the work that the Carnot cycle would produce, is dissipated, as mentioned previously by quoting A. Bejan [44],

$$s_p = q_h^\downarrow \left(\frac{1}{T_c} - \frac{1}{T_h} \right) , \quad (100)$$

consistent with eq. (95) which becomes in that case

$$q_s^\uparrow = \eta_C q_h^\downarrow = q_h^\downarrow \left(1 - \frac{T_c}{T_h} \right) . \quad (101)$$

Fig. 14. Thermodynamic diagram of a one-loop free convection $\eta_C = 1 - T_c/T_h$.

7.3.2. Example: free convection in a trapezoidal shoe-box, in 2D.

As an example, consider free 2D convection motion in a trapezoidal shoe-box, with one side higher than the other, as shown in Figure 15, filled with a given mass m of ideal gas of molar mass M . Let us consider a fluid particle of given mass $dm = \rho dV$ moving along the current. This closed micro-system is not subject to any energy exchange other than the heat exchange with the two thermal reservoirs, the heat source of temperature T_h , and the heat sink of temperature T_c , so that the processes $2 \rightarrow 3$ and $4 \rightarrow 1$ are considered adiabatic (cf. Fig. 15)

$$q_{23} = q_{41} = 0 . \quad (102)$$

with dq_{ij} the heat exchanged in the process $i \rightarrow j$ per unit mass of gas ⁵. The balance of heat exchange over a cycle is therefore

$$q^\downarrow = q_{12}^\downarrow - q_{34}^\uparrow = 0 . \quad (103)$$

The second law of thermodynamics requires that entropy production during an s_p cycle be positive since free convection is a spontaneous phenomenon and, moreover, it is strictly positive since heat transfers are irreversible

$$s_p = \frac{q_{34}^\downarrow}{T_h} - \frac{q_{12}^\uparrow}{T_c} > 0 . \quad (104)$$

Thus the heat to be absorbed on the cold side is

$$q_{34}^\uparrow = T_c \left(\frac{q_{12}^\downarrow}{T_h} + s_p \right) > q_{12}^\downarrow \frac{T_c}{T_h} . \quad (105)$$

Fig. 15. A closed streamline of free convection in a trapezoidal shoe-box coupled to two thermal reservoirs.

On the other hand, the processes $1 \rightarrow 2$ and $3 \rightarrow 4$ cannot be considered as isothermal, otherwise the cycle would be of Carnot type, and no heat exchange would be possible, as the previous section shows (cf. 7.3.1). However, let's do a test by assuming these processes are isothermal. The internal energy of an ideal gas being only a function of its temperature, it would therefore be conserved along these flow lines, and the exchange of heat with the thermal reservoir would therefore exactly compensate for the work of gravity, i.e. it would be equal to the variation of the gravitational potential energy

$$q_{12}^\downarrow = \frac{\rho_h g H_{12} dV}{\rho_h dV} = g H_{12} . \quad (106)$$

Note that the result is independent of the mass density ρ_h , given in this example by the ideal gas law

$$\rho_h = M p / T_h , \quad (107)$$

⁵ $q_{ij} = dQ_{ij}/dm$ with dQ_{ij} the exchanged heat

where p is the pressure in the shoe-box, which is uniformed in the case of an ideal flow (hypothetical fluid having a zero viscosity, consistent with the Carnot cycle). Similarly, we would also have on the cold side

$$q_{34}^\uparrow = g H_{43} . \quad (108)$$

The energy balance of a complete cycle requires $q_{12}^\downarrow = q_{34}^\uparrow$, because there can be no net work output; so, from eq. (106) and (108)

$$H_{12} = H_{43} . \quad (109)$$

Considering a trapezoidal shoe-box, as in Fig. 15, one can easily be convinced that this equality is wrong. Moreover, this calculation shows that the net work input due to gravity is globally null in steady state, as one would expect since it is a variation of the potential energy!

7.4. Production of entropy due to vibrational relaxation

The internal energy of the plasma per unit mass is decomposed according to the non-equilibrium thermodynamic modelling with constant molar mass principles given at Sect. 3.2

$$e = e_{T,R} + e_V , \quad (110)$$

where $e_{T,R}$ is the internal energy due to the degrees of freedom whose relaxation is much faster than the acoustic oscillation, i.e. mainly the rota-translational degrees of freedom, and e_V is the internal energy due to slower degrees, i.e. the vibrational degrees whose relaxation time is comparable to the acoustic period under PBF conditions, thus resulting in acoustic dispersion [21]. As entropy is an extensive property, we have also

$$s = s_{T,R} + s_V , \quad (111)$$

where $s_{T,R}$ and s_V are respectively the entropies associated with the two categories of degrees of freedom mentioned above. Moreover, the Gibbs relation can be written as, according to [17], page 214,

$$T ds_{T,R} = de_{T,R} + p \cdot d(1/\rho) , \quad (112)$$

and we have in addition

$$T_V ds_V = de_V . \quad (113)$$

Furthermore, we use the Landau-Teller theory to model the vibrational relaxation rate, in the upgraded version of Molevich et al. [45] developed to deal with medium maintained in a non-equilibrium state: a source term is added in the energy balance equation, the so called generalized heat-loss function, noted $Q - L$ in the referenced paper, which takes into account the balance of volume heat sources, between the loss L such as radiative cooling and the gain Q such as microwave heating

$$\dot{e}_V = \frac{C_V}{M} \frac{T - T_V}{\tau_V} + \dot{Q} - \dot{L} . \quad (114)$$

In this expression, M is the molar mass of the medium, C_V is the molar heat capacity due to the vibrational degrees of freedom (slow relaxation), τ_V is the corresponding relaxation time and \dot{Q} is the vibrational energy influx due to coupling with external sources, such as electromagnetic coupling that produces vibrational excitation by electronic impacts, like microwave heating for instance, and \dot{L} is the energy loss due to coupling with external heat sinks, such as radiative cooling. In the present case, as illustrated in the energy flow diagram in Fig. 10, we have

$$\dot{L} = \frac{8 \Phi^\dagger}{\rho_B V_B} = \dot{q}'_o + \dot{w}'_o \approx \dot{q}_o + \dot{w}_o , \quad (115)$$

and

$$\dot{Q} = \dot{q}_e . \quad (116)$$

Hence, eq. (114) gives, in combination with eq. (113)

$$T_V \dot{s}_V = \frac{C_V}{M} \frac{T - T_V}{\tau_V} + \frac{P_e - \Phi^\dagger}{\rho_B V_B / 8} . \quad (117)$$

Similarly, we also have

$$\dot{e}_{T,R} = T \dot{s}_{T,R} = \frac{C_V}{M} \frac{T_V - T}{\tau_V} . \quad (118)$$

The total rate of entropy variation, according to eq. (111)

$$\dot{s} = \dot{s}_{T,R} + \dot{s}_V , \quad (119)$$

is furthermore given by eq. (113) and eq. (118)

$$\dot{s} = \dot{s}_p + \frac{P_e - \Phi^\dagger}{T_V \rho_B V_B / 8} . \quad (120)$$

with \dot{s}_p the production of entropy, i.e. its variation if the system is isolated, so if $P_e = \Phi^\dagger = 0$. The production of entropy due to vibrational relaxation is according to eq. (117) and (118)

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{s}_p &= \frac{C_V}{M} \left(\frac{T_V - T}{T \tau_V} + \frac{T - T_V}{T_V \tau_V} \right) \\ &= \frac{C_V}{M \tau_V} \frac{(T_V - T)^2}{T T_V} , \end{aligned} \quad (121)$$

consistent with the second law of thermodynamic as $\dot{s}_p \geq 0$ with the zero value at and only at local thermodynamic equilibrium, i.e. under the condition $T_V = T$ [34]. In steady state, the balance of energy flux is satisfied on average, at a coarse time scale compared to the acoustic period, unlike on the acoustic time scale. Moreover, as the acoustic dispersion is notable [21], the entropy production given by eq. (121) has to be taken into account.

Fig. 16. Shape analysis of seven plasma balls. The green figures are the actual filtered optical images. The black and white images have been created with the Matlab algorithm `imbinarize(I, T)`. Each B&W figure corresponds to the optical image on its left side. An ellipse, traced in red, is manually fitted in the B&W images. The ellipses horizontal and vertical axis lengths are shown in red in Adobe Illustrator internal units. The chimney width is shown with blue. The bottom right figure shows schematically the definition of the ellipticity e_g with the horizontal (X) and vertical (Y) axes as well as the chimney width.

7.5. Photographs of PBF analysis

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